

to entire world.

dated: 15 october, 2023.

subject: coas asim munir treason puts entire us navy aircraft carriers and nuclear submarines are in danger wherever they are in any ocean.

i reported several times before headline that asim munir given secret stealth unmanned submarine technology to china. but he remain silent even his terrorist organization (pak armed forces) and police.

whatever i claimed, i proved my every word. always.

sorry to china, to save my country from terrorists (army, police, judges) i am reveling your top secret. i know because i given that ideas with technical details and minor graphical details.

basically i designed that to counter indian aircraft carriers but also keeping in mind us aircraft carriers fleets and nuclear submarine of usa ohio class and new nssn, and as usa is n. 1 enemy of pakistan. those days, 4, 5 years ago. asim munir was dg isi. and he was hafiz quran. that's why i thought he maybe loyal to almighty allah and pakistan.

the unmanned suicidal stealth sub marines.

- 1- they are made from carbon fiber to get maximum strength and zero signatures on earth magnetic fields, and acive 5000m depth.
- 2- easily equipped with 1 to 2 megaton nuclear weapon.
- 3- they have passive sensors mostly and abilities to differencing all types of sounds from fishing boat to submarines to fleet of aircraft carriers.
- 4- their unique feature that i invented was each drone submarine have a small toy size submitrine in it, which can be released from drone sub marine when he feel by his sensor lowest acoustic signatures and can be recalled any time when submarine feel some threat by his sensors. that toy submarine is attached via cable to minimum metallic material, optical fiber for communication, with copper wire to give electric current to toy submarine. both of them covered in carbon fiber composites. that gives strength to toy submarine.
- 5- role of toy submarine is to communicate via satellite, maritime petrol crafts, ships to command centers. depends on length of rope, it goes on a circle of 5 to 10kms away from parent submarine. and it has its own motors and propellers, so it can swim easily, power comes from mother submarine.
- 6- main drone submarine have low power soonars just to map the ocean bed and obstacles, to avoid collision with ocean floor or any rocks, once they reach their destination they go in sleep mode and rest on ocean bed. until next command.
- 7- main drone submarine have two type of energy sources, main source is lithium batteries on which they can travel 8000kms or more depends on kilowatts of batteries. then at 20% percent remaining battery charge it goes on ocean floor in semi sleep more with all sensors and communication toy submarine is on.
- 8- during semi sleep mode on ocean bed, it's second source of energy start working to recharge batteries, i given two ideas to recharge batteries. 1- hydrogen and oxygen tanks in it anf fuel cells to generate electricity and recharge batteries (zero noise) 2- miniature nuclear reactors

with zero noise, like used in curiosity rover, youger 1,2. and many other satellites. this system slowly charge batteries for many years.

- 9- drone submarine remain silent on ocean bed for next command.
- 10- after recharging batteries again it moves to all 10 or 12 us aircraft carriers fleets at safe distance from 50 to 100kms. every us air craft carrier fleet have 6 to 12 of these drone sub marines in their surroundings. but ocean bed. and 3,to 6 of these close to every nuclear submarine of us navy. and nato countries carrier and ships.
- 11- detection range from sonar is 100 feets approximately. can't be detected by ocean floor mapping soonar as they diflect absorb 90% sound waves and also diflect sound waves. their surface is fully covered in diamond shape zigzag patterns which are not aqua dynamic so another layer on it of sound absorbing matrial on that surface to reduce reflection of sonar waves and gives it smooth surface to sub marine to improve it's aqua dynamics.
- 12- they move on different speeds. set by command post. to reach destination waypoints it travel 6 to 12 knots. for chasing moving air craft carriers or sub marines it moves on same speed of moving target. it moving target travel very long then it send signals to command centre, so command center can assign other nearest submarines to assign targets to them, and previous drone submarine can go to ocean floor to recharge their batteries again. and other submarines who were resting on ocean floor start chasing them from same speed of enemy submarine speed. in attack mode they cross 100knots speed.
- 13- no us nato and air craft carrier, ships, submarines are safe. china can end entire us and nato navy anytime. one by one or once at a time. just one command to all these submarine.
- 14- their life is 6 to 8 years. then they can rest completely in sleep mode on ocean floor forever and new same or more modern technology same type subs.
- 15- approximately 600 these subs are recovired to cover all oceans. i don't know how many of these are built and lounched by china. maybe 1200.
- 16- estimated cost to build these under 10 million usd.
- 17- hint to save your entire navy, send it to mars. ask elon musk, space x, who is building electric cars, etc. i built my first electric car when i was a kid. under 10, with solar. panel of calculator fitted on small light weight remote control electric car of rs. 50/- equal to maybe 1 usd of that time in which car has only motor and cells are in remote connected with wire. i cutted wire and joined solar panel of calculator and stick it on top of car. and placed it under sunlight. it starts running, but not in shadow. well my goal as achieved. or breaking calculator i definitely got shoe therapy from father. :d

now it's matter of usa and nato and treason of asim munir present coas. a traitor to pakistan, allah almighty and even it's god usa and satanic jews who occupied palestinian land and doing genocide, actually their god is only money. investigate matter yourself, i given him this technology with miner drawing to show different functions and wired toy submarine function.

TREASON OF ASIM MUNIR AND CRIMES

one of them is mentioned above. 2nd treason with almighty allah and muhammad saw. 3rd is treason with muslim ummah. 4rth is with constitution of Pakistan. Intead of doing his duty to free kushmir he surrendered kashmir and started his control on everything. One every government department, judiciary etc. Actually these people is mentally abnormal people,

how can someone loyal to you (USA), who is not loyal to his God and his nation and country. stupid americans. i announced the end to you. you decide, what you want to do with this traitor. maybe pakistani courts are able enough to do anything against him, i don't think as they are followers of satan too. check their deeds. are they according to quran and sunnah or opposite? are their judgements according to quran and sunnah?

reports that i told before will release on set different dates and times. i am unvailing treason of asim munir only now, because satanic jews genocide is started on all palestinians and arabs. and pakistani elected prime minister is caged. along with 15000 his party workers. and previous army chief bajwa traitor did treason with usa's bureaucrat donald lo, cypher was prove of treason of pak army. and see our justice system, cases are on imran khan. it means the person who murdered he was not murdered he did suicide. old tactics of courts to save murderers. report consists many names of pakistan armed forces generals, core commanders, brigadiers, kernels and, generals behind begger magia, top bureaucracy of important department including wapda, ogra, nab, ace, fia, c&w, punjab, p&d punjab, fbr, army cantonments, lda, ict, brothels of pakistan (college and universities) and general involved in supplying girls, general involved in rape and murder of young girls to upload video of their rape and brutal killing on dark web. even usa nato can't save you. they can't save themselves. they are beyond their reach. and no clue of that report anywhere in my house or even in pakistan.

MY TERMS AND CONDITIONS IF ELETE CLASS WANT TO SAVE THEIR REPUTE AND LIFE. SAME AS PREVIOUS LETTER. FEW ADDITIONS, EDITS.

- 1- release imran khan and he must continue his government from where your terrorist company (pakistan army, their puppit political worker judges, especially who opened court 12 a.m, taken forcfully. he must be released immediately within 24 hours. (otherwise before big report a small report of few core commander and their summugling activities, including core commander quetta general asif ghafoor and core commander lahore who was in the planning of 9 may incidents. entire plan made in ghq and core commander lahore house was emty even security guards removed too and no staff inside house or not family members inside house. and blamed pti. son of prostitutes these general.) along with 15000+ his political workers. and as he is elected prime minister he do not need new elections until he complete his 5 years. your puppits prime ministers shehbaz shareef or kukar are not accepted and nor their governments.
- 2- release and restore dr. afia siddiqui to her home in pakistan. within 36 hours, you son of prostitutes, your general mushraf accepted that he sold dr. afia siddiqui to usa. but no media will be allowed to go and interview her. and apology letter from entire pakistan army for dr. afia siddiqui to me, which i will bring to her and ask for forgiveness for crimes of pakistan army.

- 3- immediate sentence of death to chief justice qazi faiz essa and must be hanged outside supreme court in crime of betraying allah, rasool allah saw, along with molana tariq jameel of same crime.
- 4- give name of nawaz sharif to interpol, capture him and mariam his daughter. do what they did with arshad shareef shaheed. with live broadcasting on all channels.
- 5- all bureaucracy of pakistan will be changed with a.i. in starting secretary of c&w, irrigation and planning and development, then comissioners, deputy commissioner, assistant commissioner. until imam mahdi comes thrn he can end a.i. and not us made a.i. programming is everything. chinese a.i only.
- 6- pakistani nation never taken any debts from evil banks and organizations of the worlds imf, world bank, asian development bank. if any loan is taken behind every crime there are pak army generals. and these generals will pay all drbitfrom their reserves in foreign banks. which is over 800 billion usd. pakistani citizens must not charge any more. sell all dha's, golf courts, cantonments on civilian areas, factories of army personnels, properties of army personnels. no free electricity to anyone including president and coas, chairman wapda. anyone. build your cantonment out of population and near to borders.
- 7- end of interest based economy system.
- 8- pakistan nation will pay fix rate of electricity including all taxes rs. 10/unite pkr. and rs. 80/litre for petrol and rs. 82/litre for diesel, 1/10th of gas prices of 9th october, 2023.
- 9- gas prices. rs. 60/ kg of lpg.
- 10- replacement of russian embassy with usa's embassy. with only 3 person staff of us embassy. kick all other us emassy members in arabian sea near fake dead body of osama bin ladin.
- 11- all hec and pec officials and bureaucrats will clean roads and sewers of pindi and other cities of pakistan undar staff of cleaning workers. it is most better job than what they are doing now.
- 12- technical allowance to all diploma engineers on duty. which was approved but still given to anyone in punjab especially.
- 13- no ex military or on duty military official will ever serve any civilian department, university, college etc.
- 14- to bureaucrats of c&w department you will pay of my 14 years service and my father's car's service and operational charges plus fine total 1 billion sr. in next 48 hours after 48 hours 10% fine will be added every 24 hours. it is international rule to provide 4x4, petrol,

any safety equipment for self defense for rural areas, civil engineering equipments, you never given us ordinary plastic measurement tape. not even computer not even stationery. i wrote many times to them in reports. but what they did? attempts to kill me. in my 14 years i didn't get a rim of papers to print detailed estimate for the department. everything we used from our own pocket. try to delay as much as possible. fine will increase. and then most probably i change sr to usd or kuwairi dinar. this is not fine of your crimes and corruption. this is fine because in my official previous letter i just asked for operational charges of my father's car, because it was your duty to provide vehicle with petrol, even your secretary musa raza promised me to provide 4x4 and petrol monthly. but never given one liter of petrol. that letter posted on 10-10-2023. (today is 15th. 30% fine added.) i will punish you . and this is fine to all of you. not government of pakistan. so you will pay from your reserves in swiss banks. not from national treasury.

now previous request time over. and it is not request. it's order, and i am always ready for next move.

REQUEST TO HONEST LAWYERS OF PAKISTAN.

i want to file case on all ullema of pakistan who telling greatness of muhammad saw, ali rz, omar rz, and others in hours long lectures and other all topics of the world. but in 76 years of pakistan they never implemented or forced government to implement islamic government, laws and

complete islamic economic system. and army who help all muslims of the world. pak army is rental army who pays them more they work for them and kill it's own civilians and arrest them via police department and then torture them. here are millions of molanas, muftis, peers, ullema and hafiz etc?

is there duty is to just open madressa or join madressa of any sect and do their business? or their duty is to implement deen islam with full power. allah made prophet muhammad saw mercy on mankind for all worlds. are you more merciful than muhammad saw? or manifiq? allah almighty said fight to implement my deen islam, prophet muhammad saw fought 30 or 40 battles ghazwas. to implement rule of allah. who are you? who is your god?

then collecting trillions on the name of allah and rasool allah saw, and absolutely zero tax and accountability on them. why? did they implemented islam in pakistan? it is their duty? or usa come and implement islam in pakistan?

pakistan nation need food, healthcare, safety, immediate justice, law and order implementation, safety of women, children, even if a mother with her child walking alone in middle of night, international standard education, jobs, safe drinking water, electricity with justified rates. rate of everything justified. what they are doing for us for our basic needs extremely high prices, more and more taxes of government. if you cannot fight for your basic human rights. then tell pakistani nation to not follow them until they do their duty. by supreme court or high court. which is better for this type case.

after all these we can listen your lectures which you are giving to yourselves, and will obey. everyone in pakistan is god. who have some power he/she use all his/her power in full potential to mostly harm other for their personal benefits. everyone is god in pakistan. do you know why? no rule of law.

this is my case. if these ullema, muftis, allamas, peers, cannot implement islam in pakistan than who given them right to collect money on the name of allah, rasool allah saw? then they are hypocrites.

but first i give a chance to everyone to repent and do thier work correctly (i given this chance to asim munir two times in writing but he ignored and showed more cruelty and as their heart was broken because they were officially accepting israel and allah showed his plan and their plans failed, see face of asim munir and his companion doesn't they look like satan, especially after attack of hamas on terrorist jews? same chance will be given to them. for certain time limit.

sorry i don't have money to pay you. only precious thing is my father car model 2002 suzuki alto. and it is still on name my father. i will gift it to you.

TO TALIBAN GOVERNMENT

didn't i said pakistani generals, brigadiers, kernels etc are hypocrites even solders of army who obey them. according to quran and sunah you need to fight first with munafiqeen first of all as per sunah. then go to palestine and kill all terrorist jews. read sunnah. read history. yes you can fight on both sides at a time if you can fight.

occupied forces of palestinian land face shortage of artillery rounds, because they and nao countries recently used their stockpiles of ammunition. now west is running short of ammunition. great opportunity for pak army generals, and pof wah. maybe they were suppling ammunition to them secretly.

TO RUSSIA, CHINA AND KSA. (ONLY TRUE FRIENDS OF PAKISTAN)

maybe you surprised as a said russia as a friend. but he want to be they are not like americans nor like they were in ussr era.

thanks to all of you. i don't need asylum in your country. my life is in more danger now. but i am fully satisfied. if i am killed i will be shaheed, if aressted and tortured then i am ghazi, if my relatives kidnapped by them. i will not ask to return them to me.

i submitted my life, my body, my relatives, my wealth (i don't have any money, i paid court case fees to lawyer by selling my only ac of my bedroom. then i purchased a water evaporation based low cost cooler on instalments.

it is pakistan army's nature to kill and kidnap people and beat them on open public by paid terrorists.

international community play some role 240 millions pakistanis are suffering due to 1% elite class.

TO ARGENTINA

i had a friend from argentina who was female headmaster of some school. years ago. she was twice in age than me. she told me about problem of argentina, drugs in schools etc. now she maybe not alive. and i do not have contact number of her. around 15 years ago.

don't trap in usa carrot and stick trap, stay away from usa for your betterment. if they want to give you new f-35s full free of cost. then to reject us offer. first they bribe you to buy you then they sell their things to you then whenever they want they will show you your sins and black mail you more. two weapons they use to bribe (money, girls).

don't buy old tech rusted f-16s. jf-17 block 3 is far superior to rafael, euro fighter and f-16s block 60, they are slightly less than block 70. but much better in multipurpose use, price, operational cost, maintenance etc. i am a scientist. i know better. usa can be sunk with click of one button.

usa is ended.

china is bigger power and china don't black mail you like americans, chinese policy is clear. development. progress. peace.

just a suggestion. choice is your's . if usa is friendly to you then why they was not giving you those old rusted f-16s before? usa is evil. better to say goodbye bye to usa and imf. no need to pay your loans. which is on interest based.

TO CROWN PRINCE MUHAMMAD BIN SALMAN,

you are good man by heart, in last few years you learned alot and as much you got knowledge of real things you changed you policies. now you are progressing more.

please help palestinians, i am fighting with life of myself and family, with all my money. mostly empty pockets. wealth is not money, gold, places made of gold, i prefer hut made from mud for my self.

money is lowest type of wealth. original wealth is faith on almighty allah, honesty, moral values, living style, talking style. my talking style is very soft. but my writing style is like doing wrestling :d, take care of yourself. usa and stanic jews living in palestine are planning against you. i don't have any news. it's my intuition.

please take care of yourself. we love you.

TO UKRAINE

it's better to be part of russia. you both are from same race, same tribes. zelesnky is jew.

decide your fate. do referendum.

TO STANDFORD UNIVERSITY, USA.

months ago i given challenge to you to give me one example of your university students, who have such level of courage, honesty, understanding of science and technology, i learned quran with help of science and technology and to understand science and technology quran was best guide, self educated. only diploma in civil engineering. and just given exams of b.a geography and sociology. i was educated by quran. with any other person or scholar. still i am a student and hungry of knowledge. do you ever produced man like me? if yes please introduce him to me. i really want to meet him happily. You can produce scientists but slaves. With no courage to fight against evil.

ONE IMPORTANT THING TO SHARE.

a picture and it's analysis.

Place of picture. Outside grill of place where Prophet Muhammad SAW grave is present.

This is very popular picture of General Asif Ghafoor, Present Core Commander Quetta. His other crimes with proves are in other reports in approximately catedched tops elite class corrupt people.

Well. Very inspiring picture. Yeah ??? Lets analyze it. Doing anything other than already told word of doing slaam and Darood, whatever is told. I memorized it years ago. But now i forget. While he is doing Salute with especially Photographer not even mobile canera, DSLR Camera, see flash of camera reflection of white light of flash on grill and his face. Simple he hired a photographer i did photography 30 years, but as hobby. So, check angle of taking photograph and why he is doing Salute? Want to show that he is more loyal and he is solder of prophet Muhammad SAW? While doing anything including salute is prohibited there. But people of Pakistan are illiterate mostly. These things inpire people. He is catching fame and reputation only in Pakistani people.

When i did umrah and first time i reached there and memorized what is allowed to say and how. Traveling in line when i reached there a verse of Quran came in my mind. In which Allah almighty warned people “ do not talk louder than Voice of Prophet Muhammad SAW, otherwise you may not know and your all good deeds are wiped out” i started fear in my full body as much i was getting closer to grill, i thought if i prayed in normal or vern low voice then to my voice will be higher as he is dead now. Now he can't speak directly. I prayed dua in my heart not by mouth, I did not stopped there, feeling extreme fear, where i am standing? In front of Muhammad PBUH Grave, i was feeling i am standing in front of him and started feeling fear due to my sins and disobedience to his Sunah (not fully, but ordinary man, with ordinary sins), and then i left i called my travel agent to arrange bus for me i want to return to Makkah, he said your stay in medina is 10 days, i said no, i want to leave. Well he arranged after 2 days. But i didn't again went there due to fear. I thought when standing in front physically dead Muhammad PBUH, gives me that fear what will happen to me when i was alone in front of Almighty with my book of deeds in my hand And Allah Lord of All universes will say, read this book. What was my condition of fear on that time? Judgement Day. After returning Pakistan. I felt that maybe i did disrespect to Prophet Muhammad SAW, as not staying there for ten days, and not going on that place again and again. Then i asked Almighty Allah to deiver my forgiveness message to Muhammad PBUH, that i am ssking for forgiveness from him to not coming there again and again. And i am completely ordinary man with normal deeds. Not very religious

Japan, or any country

you have shortage of new generation, pakistani people are raw materials, educated or not. if you want to give visa's to pakistani people. then prefer full family visas with their children but put one condition on them after reaching japan, they must learn first honesty, rule of law, moral values, ethics then give permanent visas after some time monitoring their activities.

they are good people by heart. but bad corrupt pakistan system destroyed them and hypocrite islamic scholars of pakistan .

Best wishes to everyone on earth pray for muslims that they follow rule and law of their God, otherwise they will ne killed everywhere. They can rise only if they ,”Hold string of Almighty Allah and don’t make sects” Quran and that string is also Quran.
This is only solution to their all problems.

my previous reports.

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1k8572ezwsifabxdzflcclxw7cnn9u4tf/view?usp=drivesdk>

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